

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE ENERGY-SAVING COATINGS IN BUILDINGS AND STRUCTURES

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Abstract: The article describes the results of experimental studies on the analysis and improvement of existing methods for determining thermal conductivity. Covering non-textured surfaces with perfectly heat-retaining coatings, methods of efficient use of heat are highlighted.

Key words: *microsphere, energy efficiency, modern heat-retaining coatings, thermal conductivity, requirements for heat-retaining coatings, advantages and areas of application of liquid heat-retaining coatings.*

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Introduction

In our nation, there is a rising annual demand for materials that retain heat. These materials are produced in accordance with rigorous specifications. They are first and foremost environmentally friendly, flexible, energy-efficient, small in size, light, and resistant to decay (corrosion) when applied to iron products and buildings. They also reduce heat loss and offer mold protection when applied to structures. Saving heat and cutting energy use in manufacturing and large industrial facilities are currently regarded as critical and significant challenges. [1]

Fiberglass is currently utilized to conserve heat and use it effectively. If we take urban thermal power plants as an example, bitumen is first put to the pipes to keep the heat within, followed by the wrapping and covering of zinc and fiberglass. From an economic perspective, this will be very time- and money-consuming.

Our cutting-edge heat-retaining material is exceptional in that it may be used in all areas of industry in addition to buildings, structures, and heat pipes.

Picture 1. Uniform adhesion of heat-retaining coating to any material.

This substance is created using microspheres and acrylic paints (a few other chemicals). It can be applied to any surface and has good adhesion (to materials such as brick, glass-to-glass, metall, plastic, gypsum, cement-sand regions, concrete, and wood). It also inhibits corrosion on cold surfaces. is unique in that it lays. Picture 1

Because the surface is unusual, that is, it is incompatible with the typical heat-retaining substance (glass wool), we are aware that covering uneven surfaces with heat-retaining materials is a very difficult operation. We will get large amounts if we calculate the heat loss on uneven surfaces that are not

covered. We are performing scientific research on a novel heat-retaining pencil that can adapt to even complicated surfaces. Picture 2 [2]

Analysis

We initially became familiar with heat-retentive coatings imported into our nation from other nations. The exceptionally low heat transfer coefficient of these paints can be used to explain why they are receiving so much attention. For instance, the thermal conductivity coefficient of “Bronya” paint is $0.001 \text{ Wt/m} \cdot ^\circ\text{S}$ and that of “Corund” paint is $0.001 \text{ Wt/m} \cdot ^\circ\text{S}$ [2]. Naturally, this coefficient of thermal conductivity favors heat-insulating coatings over conventional heaters

(extruded polystyrene foam, mineral cotton, etc.), so the extruded polystyrene foam has a coefficient of thermal conductivity of $0.030 \text{ Wt/m} \cdot ^\circ\text{S}$.

The lack of standardized procedures for evaluating the coefficient of heat conductivity of novel ultra-thin coatings based on microspheres can be used to explain discrepancies in the results that were obtained. All of these paints have grids of hollow microspheres joined by elements that form an acrylic film as their structural component.

Picture 2. Coating on surfaces considered to be complex

Because of this, numerous experiments have been carried out to ascertain the thermal characteristics and effectiveness of these paints. The value of the coefficient of thermal conductivity of liquid thermal insulation coatings has attracted the interest of both consumers and researchers.

The thermal conductivity of air is $0.026 \text{ Wt/m} \cdot ^\circ\text{S}$ under normal circumstances, while the thermal conductivity of a vacuum is $0 \text{ Wt/m} \cdot ^\circ\text{S}$ [2]. The most effective natural heat insulator is air [2].

One of the most pressing challenges at this time is figuring out the exact heat transfer coefficient of liquid thermal insulation coatings.

Therefore, research is being done at the Fergana Polytechnic Institute's "Youth Innovative Technologies Center" on the application of thin, contemporary heat-retaining coatings, the measurement of heat transfer coefficients, and their improvement. This novel material may provide a solution to the aforementioned issues.

Method

heat meter was intended to be replaced with a layer of material with a clear coefficient of thermal conductivity using the standard method of calculating the coefficient of thermal conductivity of liquid heat insulation coatings, based on an analysis of the methods used during the experiments. The theory of thermal process research is not in conflict with such a replacement.

The method for calculating the coating's coefficient of thermal conductivity is as follows:

The coefficient of thermal conductivity of the liquid thermal insulation coating was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\lambda = \frac{d_u}{\frac{\Delta T_u}{q_u} - 2R_L},$$

Here d_u - thickness at the time of testing the sample, m;

ΔT_u - temperature difference on the surfaces of the tested sample $^\circ\text{S}$;

q_u - stationary heat flux density passing through the tested sample, Wt/m^2 ;

R_L - thermal resistance of the tested sample (paint) coated copper plate, $(m^2 \cdot ^\circ S)/Vt$

Stationary heat flux density passing through the sample q_u , is found from the following formula:

$$q_u = \frac{\lambda_{2qatlam(t_1-t_2)}}{\delta_{2qatlam}}, \text{ Vt/m}^2$$

Here λ and δ – coefficient of thermal conductivity and thickness of orgsteklon t_1, t_2 – temperature at the limits of "heat source - plexiglass layer" and "plexiglass layer - test sample", respectively.

Thickness $\delta = 0,5$ mm thermal conductivity of the copper plate $\lambda = 384$ Vt/(m \cdot °S) is equal to

Conclusion

In conclusion, we must say that saving heat is one of the most urgent issues today. It is especially effective if it is applied to modern houses under construction. In our country, the winter season does not last long, but this coating helps to keep not only heat, but also coolness in summer.

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